

Group Connectivity of 1-Edge Deletable IM-Extendable Graphs

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Abstract: A graph G is called a k -edges deletable IM-extendable graph, if $G - F$ is IM-extendable for every $F \subseteq E(G)$ with $|F| = k$. Denoted by $\wedge_g(G)$ the group connectivity of a graph G . In this paper, $\wedge_g(G) = 3$ is gotten if G is a 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph.

Key Words: Graph, multi-group connectivity, group connectivity, induced matching.

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§1. Introduction and Lemmas

In 1950s, Tutte introduced the theory of nowhere-zero flows as a tool to investigate the coloring problem of maps, together with his most fascinating conjectures on nowhere-zero flows. These have been extended by Jaeger, Linial, Payan and Tarsil in 1992 to group connectivity, the generalized form of nowhere-zero flows. Let G be an undirected graph and $\tilde{A} = (\bigcup_{i=1}^m A_i; \{+_i, 1 \leq i \leq m\})$ be an Abelian multi-group. Let \tilde{A}^* denote the set of non-zero elements of \tilde{A} . A function $b : V(G) \rightarrow \tilde{A}$ is called an \tilde{A} -valued zero-sum function of G if $\sum_{v \in V(G)} b(v) = 0_{+_i}, 1 \leq i \leq m$ in G . The set of all \tilde{A} -valued zero-sum function on G is denoted by $Z(G, \tilde{A})$. We define: $F(G, \tilde{A}) = \{f : E(G) \rightarrow \tilde{A}\}$ and $F^*(G, \tilde{A}) = \{f : E(G) \rightarrow \tilde{A}^*\}$. Let G^1 be an orientation of a graph G . If an edge $e \in E(G)$ is directed from a vertex u to a vertex v , then let $\text{tail}(e) = u$ and $\text{head}(e) = v$. For a vertex $v \in V(G)$, let $E^-(v) = \{e \in E(G^1) : v = \text{tail}(e)\}$, and $E^+(v) = \{e \in E(G^1) : v = \text{head}(e)\}$. Given a function $f \in F(G, \tilde{A})$, define $\partial f : V(G) \rightarrow \tilde{A}$ by $\partial f(v) = \sum_{e \in E^+(v)} f(e) - \sum_{e \in E^-(v)} f(e)$. A graph G is \tilde{A} -connected if G has an orientation G^1 such that for every function $b \in Z(G, \tilde{A})$, there is a function $f \in F^*(G^1, \tilde{A})$ such that $b = \partial f$. Let $\langle \tilde{A} \rangle$ be the family of graphs that are \tilde{A} -connected. The *multi-group connectivity* of G is defined as: $\wedge_g(G) = \min\{k \mid \text{if } \tilde{A} \text{ is an Abelian group with } |\tilde{A}| \geq k, \text{ then } G \in \langle \tilde{A} \rangle\}$. Particularly,

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if $m = 1$, i.e., $\tilde{A} = (A, +)$ an Abelian group, such connectivity is called *group connectivity*.

Let v be a vertex of G , denote $N(v)$ by $N(v) = \{u \in V(G) - v : uv \in E(G)\}$. Let u be a vertex of G , denote $N^2(u) = N(N(u)) \setminus (N(u) \cup \{u\})$. Graph G is called *claw-free*, if it doesn't contain $K_{1,3}$ as an induced subgraph. Let C_n^k denote the graph with $V(C_n^k) = V(C_n)$, $E(C_n^k) = \{uv : u, v \in V(C_n) \text{ and } d_{C_n}(u, v) \leq k\}$, where $d_{C_n}(u, v)$ is a distance between u and v in C_n . Let G be a graph. A *triangle-path* in G is a sequence of distinct triangles $T_1 T_2 \cdots T_m$ in G such that for $1 \leq i \leq m - 1$, the following formula (*) holds:

$$|E(T_i) \cap E(T_{i+1})| = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad E(T_i) \cap E(T_j) = \emptyset \quad \text{if } j > i + 1. \quad (*)$$

Furthermore, if $m \geq 3$ and (*) holds for all i , $1 \leq i \leq m$, with the additionally taken mod m , then the sequence is called a *triangle-cycle*. The number m is the length of the triangle-path(triangle-cycle). A connected graph G is *triangularly connected* if for any distinct $e, e_1 \in E(G)$, which are not parallel, there is a triangle-path $T_1 T_2 \cdots T_m$ such that $e \in E(T_1)$ and $e_1 \in E(T_m)$.

Let G be a connected graph, $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ denote its sets of vertices and edges, respectively. For $S \subseteq V(G)$, let $E(S) = \{uv \in E(G), u, v \in S\}$. For $M \subseteq E(G)$, let $V(M) = \{u \in V(G) : \text{there is } v \in V(G) \text{ such that } uv \in M\}$. A set of edges $M \subseteq E(G)$ is called a *matching* of G if they are independent in G , and no two of them share a common end vertex. A matching is called *perfect* if it covers all vertices of G . A matching M is called induced matching if $E(V(M)) = M$. G is called *induced matching extendable* if every induced matching M of G is contained in a perfect matching of G . For simplicity, induced matching extendable will often be abbreviated as *IM-extendable*.

Notations undefined in this paper will follow [1]. In this paper, we give some properties of the 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable and prove that its group connectivity is 3.

Lemma 1.1.([1]) *A graph G has a perfect matching if and only if for every $S \subseteq V(G)$, $o(G-S) \leq |S|$, Where $o(H)$ is the number of odd components of H .*

For group connectivity, some conclusions have reached. For example, complete graphs, complete bipartite graphs and triangularly connected graphs etc in [2,3,4,5,6]. For more results about IM-extendable graphs, one can see references [7,8,9,10].

A *k-circuit* is a circuit of k vertices. A *wheel* W_k is the graph obtained from a k -circuit by adding a new vertex, called the center of the wheel, which is joined to every vertex of the k -circuit. W_k is an odd(even) wheel if k is odd(even). For a technical reason, a single edge is regarded as 1-circuit, and thus W_1 is a triangle, called the trivial wheel.

Lemma 1.2([6]) (1) $W_{2n} \in \langle Z_3 \rangle$.

(2) Let $G \cong W_{2n+1}$, $b \in Z(G, Z_3)$. Then there exists a (Z_3, b) -NZF $f \in F^*(G, Z_3)$ if and only if $b \neq 0$.

Lemma 1.3([4]) *Let G be a connected graph with n vertices and m edges. Then $\wedge_g(G) = 2$ if and only if $n = 1$ (and so G has m loops).*

Lemma 1.4([3]) *Let $H \leq G$ be Z_k -connected. If G/H is Z_k -connected, then so is G .*

§2. Main Results

Lemma 2.1 C_6^2 is 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable connected IM-extendable graph.

Proof Obviously, C_6^2 is 4-regular and claw-free. The following we will prove C_6^2 is 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph. Supposing the vertices of C_6^2 denoted by v_i , $1 \leq i \leq 6$, along a clockwise. Supposing M is an induced matching of an induced graph $G[N(u)]$. Since $G[N(u)]$ has four vertices, so $|M| \leq 2$. If $|M| = 2$, u is an isolated vertex of $G - V(M)$, this conflict with that G is 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph, thus, $|M| \leq 1$. Since $E(C_6^2) = E_1 \cup E_2$ where $E_1 = E(C_6)$, $E_2 = E \setminus E_1$, the following discussions are divided into two cases.

Case 1 Deleting one edge in E_1 . Without loss of generality, suppose deleting edge v_1v_2 . From the structure of C_6^2 , if M is an induced matching of C_6^2 , then $|M| < 2$. If let $M = v_2v_3$ be an induced matching of $G - \{v_1v_2\}$, it extended to a perfect matching $\{v_2v_3, v_4v_5, v_6v_1\}$. Otherwise, let $M = \{v_2v_4\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{v_1v_2\}$, it extended to a perfect matching $\{v_2v_4, v_3v_5, v_6v_1\}$.

Case 2 Deleting one edge in E_2 . Without loss of generality, let $M = \{v_2v_3\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{v_1v_3\}$, it extended to a perfect matching $\{v_2v_3, v_4v_5, v_6v_1\}$. Otherwise, let $M = \{v_3v_5\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{v_1v_3\}$, it extended to a perfect matching $\{v_3v_5, v_2v_4, v_6v_1\}$. So C_6^2 is a 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable connected IM-extendable graph. \square

Lemma 2.2 Let G be a 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable connected IM-extendable graph, then $G = C_6^2$.

Proof For a given $u \in V(G)$, since G is 4-regular, let $N(u) = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4\}$, $N^2(u) = N(N(u)) \setminus (N(u) \cup \{u\})$, $f(u) = |E(N(u))|$, $g(N(u)) = |N^2(u)|$.

Since G is 4-regular and claw-free, we have $2 \leq f(u) \leq 6$. If $f(u) = 6$, G is isomorphic to K_5 , there is no perfect matching in K_5 which is a contradiction with 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph. If $f(u) = 5$, $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to $K_4 - e$. Without loss of generality, let $e = x_2x_4$ and $y_1 \in N(x_2) \setminus (\{u\} \cup N(u))$. Since G is 4-regular, there exists $z \in N(y_1) \setminus N(u)$. Let $M = \{y_1z, ux_1\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$. It could not extend to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$ which is a contradiction. Next we discuss: $2 \leq f(u) \leq 4$. There are three cases according to the value of $f(u)$.

Case 1 $f(u) = 2$.

Let x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 be neighbor vertices of u , we have three different subcases: Subcase(a) $x_1x_2, x_2x_3 \in E(G)$; Subcase(b) $x_1x_2, x_3x_4 \in E(G)$; Subcase(c) $x_1x_2, x_1x_3 \in E(G)$.

For subcases (a), the induced subgraph of G by vertices u, x_1, x_3, x_4 consists of an induced subgraph $k_{1,3}$ which contradict with the assumption. For subcase (b), $M = \{x_1x_2, x_3x_4\}$ is an induced matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$, however, u could not included in vertex set of any perfect matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$ which contradict with the assumption. For subcase (c), the induced subgraph of G by vertices u, x_2, x_3, x_4 consists of $k_{1,3}$, which contradicts with the assumption. Therefore $f(u) \neq 2$.

Case 2 $f(u) = 3$.

$G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to P_4 or $K_3 \cup K_1$ or $K_{1,3}$, where P_n is the path with n vertices.

If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to P_4 . Supposing $x_1x_2, x_2x_3, x_3x_4 \in E(G)$, then $M = \{x_1x_2, x_3x_4\}$ is an induced matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$, but it does not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$.

If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to $k_{1,3}$, obviously G consists of $k_{1,3}$ as its induced subgraph, contradiction.

If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to $K_3 \cup K_1$, supposing $x_1x_2, x_2x_3, x_1x_3 \in E(G)$, then $3 \leq g(N(u)) \leq 6$, there are four subcases according to the value of $g(N(u))$.

Subcase 1. If $g(N(u)) = 3$, let $N^2(u) = \{y_1, y_2, y_3\}$ then $y_ix_4 \in E(G)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$). Since G is claw-free and 4-regular, then $y_1y_2, y_1y_3, y_2y_3 \in E(G)$ and each vertex of x_i is adjacent to only one vertices of y_j (where $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are distinct). Without loss of generality, let x_1, x_2, x_3 are adjacent to y_1, y_2, y_3 respectively. Let $M = \{x_1x_3, x_4y_2\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$. It does not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$ which is a contradiction.

Subcase 2. If $g(N(u)) = 4$, let $y_i \in N^2(u), i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Since $d(x_4) = 4$, there is three of $y_i (1 \leq i \leq 4)$ adjacent to x_4 , without loss of generality, supposing $y_ix_4 \in E(G)$ ($i = 2, 3, 4$). Because G is claw-free, one have $y_2y_3, y_3y_4, y_2y_4 \in E(G)$. Obviously y_1 is adjacent to at least one vertex of x_i ($i=1,2,3$).

If y_1 is adjacent to each of x_i ($i=1,2,3$), that is $x_1y_1, x_2y_1, x_3y_1 \in E(G)$. If $y_1y_4 \notin E(G)$, let $M = \{x_1y_1, x_4y_4\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$. If $y_1y_4 \in E(G)$, let $M = \{x_1y_1, x_4y_3\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_2x_3\}$.

If y_1 is adjacent to two vertices of x_i ($i=1,2,3$), without loss of generality, let $x_1y_1, x_2y_1 \in E(G)$ and $x_3y_1 \notin E(G)$, x_3 is adjacent to one of y_i (which $i \in \{2, 3, 4\}$). If $x_3y_3 \notin E(G)$, let $M = \{x_2x_3, x_4y_3\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{y_2y_4\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{y_2y_4\}$. If $x_3y_3 \in E(G)$, let $M = \{x_2x_3, x_4y_4\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_1\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_1\}$.

If y_1 is adjacent to only one of x_i ($i=1,2,3$), without loss of generality, let $x_1y_1 \in E(G)$. Supposing $x_2y_2, x_3y_3 \in E(G)$, let $M = \{x_1x_2, x_4y_3\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_3\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_3\}$.

Subcase 3. If $g(N(u)) = 5$, let $N^2(u) = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5\}$ and supposing $y_3x_4, y_4x_4, y_5x_4 \in E(G)$. Because G is claw-free, $y_3y_4, y_4y_5, y_5y_3 \in E(G)$. Since no more than two vertices of x_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) is adjacent to y_j ($j = 1, 2$), without loss of generality, let $x_1y_1, x_2y_2 \in E(G)$.

If x_3 is adjacent to y_1 or y_2 , supposing $x_3y_1 \in E(G)$. Let $M = \{x_1x_3, x_4y_3\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$. It does not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$ which is a contradiction.

If $x_3y_i \notin E(G)$ ($i=1,2$). Without loss of generality, supposing $x_3y_3 \in E(G)$. Let $M = \{x_1x_3, x_4y_5\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$.

Subcase 4. If $g(N(u)) = 6$, without loss of generality, supposing $y_ix_4 \in E(G)$ ($i = 4, 5, 6$).

Because each vertex of x_i ($i=1,2,3$) has degree 3 in $N(u)$, each of x_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) is adjacent to only one of y_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$), without loss of generality, let $x_i y_i \in E(G)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$). Let $M = \{x_1 x_3, x_4 y_4\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{u x_2\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{u x_2\}$. So $f(u) \neq 3$.

Case 3 If $f(u) = 4$, $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to C_4 or $K_{1,3} + e$.

If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to C_4 . Since there are only four edges between $N(u)$ and $N^2(u)$, then $1 \leq g(N(u)) \leq 4$.

(3.1) If $g(N(u)) = 1$. Supposing $v \in N^2(u)$, there exists $x_i v \in E(G)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$), it is isomorphic to C_6^2 .

(3.2) If $g(N(u)) = 2$. Supposing $y_1, y_2 \in N^2(u)$. There are two subcases. Subcases 1, there are two vertices adjacent to y_1 , two vertices adjacent to y_2 . Subcases 2, there are three vertices adjacent to y_1 , only one vertex adjacent to y_2 .

Subcase 1. Supposing $x_1 y_1, x_2 y_1, x_3 y_2, x_4 y_2 \in E(G)$, there exists z , satisfying $y_1 z \in E(G)$. Let $M = \{x_3 x_4, y_1 z\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_1 x_2\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_1 x_2\}$.

Subcase 2. Supposing $x_1 y_1, x_2 y_1, x_3 y_1, x_4 y_2 \in E(G)$. However, x_4, x_3, x_1, y_2 induced a $K_{1,3}$ which is a contradiction.

(3.3) If $g(N(u)) = 3$. Supposing $y_1, y_2, y_3 \in N^2(u)$. Obviously, only two vertices of x_i ($i=1,2,3,4$) are adjacent to one of y_i ($i=1,2,3$). Without loss of generality, let $x_i y_i, x_4 y_3 \in E(G)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$). x_2, x_1, y_2, x_3 induced a $K_{1,3}$ which is a contradiction.

(3.4) If $g(N(u)) = 4$. Supposing $y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4 \in N^2(u)$. Without loss of generality, let $x_i y_i \in E(G)$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$). x_2, x_1, y_1, x_4 induced a $K_{1,3}$ subgraph. If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to C_4 , it does not extended to a perfect matching. If $G[N(u)]$ is isomorphic to $K_{1,3} + e$, supposing $x_1 x_2, x_1 x_3, x_1 x_4, x_3 x_4 \in E(G)$, since there are only 4 edges between $N(u)$ and $N^2(u)$, one have $2 \leq g(N(u)) \leq 4$. There are three subcases according to the value of $g(N(u))$.

Subcase 1. If $g(N(u)) = 2$. Supposing $N^2(u) = \{y_1, y_2\}$, then $x_2 y_1, x_2 y_2 \in E(G)$. Because G is claw-free, $y_1 y_2 \in E(G)$. If both of x_3, x_4 are adjacent to y_1 , let $M = \{u x_1, y_1 y_2\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_3 x_4\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_3 x_4\}$. If $x_3 y_1, x_4 y_2 \in E(G)$, let $M = \{u x_1, y_1 y_2\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_3 x_4\}$ which could not extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{x_3 x_4\}$.

Subcase 2. If $g(N(u)) = 3$, supposing $N^2(u) = \{y_1, y_2, y_3\}$. Without loss of generality, let $x_2 y_1, x_2 y_2 \in E(G)$. Because G is claw-free, $y_1 y_2 \in E(G)$. If both of x_3, x_4 are adjacent to y_3 , let $M = \{y_1 y_2, x_3 x_4\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_1 x_3\}$. However, not all vertices of x_1, x_2, u could be included in a perfect matching vertices of $G - \{x_1 x_3\}$ which is a contradiction. If $x_3 y_3, x_4 y_2 \in E(G)$, let $M = \{x_1 x_3, y_1 y_2\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{x_1 x_2\}$. However, not all vertices of x_2, x_4, u could be included in a vertex set of perfect matching of $G - \{x_1 x_1\}$ which is a contradiction.

Subcase 3. If $g(N(u)) = 4$, Supposing $N^2(u) = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4\}$. Without loss of generality,

let $x_2y_1, x_2y_2, x_3y_3, x_4y_4 \in E(G)$. Because G is claw-free, $y_1y_2 \in E(G)$. Let $M = \{x_1x_4, y_1y_2 \in E(G)\}$ be an induced matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$ which could not be extended to a perfect matching of $G - \{ux_2\}$. The lemma 2.2 is proved. \square

Lemma 2.3 *If $n \geq 5$, then C_n^2 is Z_3 -connected.*

Proof By the definition of C_n^k , for $n \geq 5$, there exists a subgraph of C_n^2 isomorphic to W_{2k} . By lemma 1.2, W_{2k} is Z_3 -connected. Since C_n^2 is triangularly connected, by contracting W_{2k} in C_n^2 and Lemma 1.4, we have C_n^2 is Z_3 -connected. \square

Theorem 2.4 *The group connectivity of 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph is 3.*

Proof By applying lemma 2.1 and lemma 2.2, 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph is C_6^2 . From Lemma 2.3, the group connectivity of 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph is not more than 3. By lemma 1.3 we conclude the group connectivity of 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph is more than 2. Therefore, the group connectivity of 4-regular claw-free 1-edge deletable IM-extendable graph is 3. This theorem is proved. \square

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